

The Role of Environmental, Social and Governance in Workplace – With Special Reference to Universal Automobile and Dairy Product. Mysore

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Abstract:

ESG is a framework used to evaluate the sustainable and ethical impact of an organization, investment or business practices. The integration of environmental, social and governance considerations into workplace practices has become increasingly important for business seeking to enhance their sustainability, employee engagement and overall performance. It provides a framework for organizations to manage risks and opportunities related to sustainability issues. This overview of ESG has highlighted the key components of ESG, its importance in today's world, and how it has evolved over time. ESG issues for employees include fair wages, safe conditions, rights, diversity, inclusion, training, and work-life balance, requiring a supportive workplace culture, fair compensation, occupational health, and professional growth opportunities. The present study was found that employees are properly utilizing the available benefits of ESG and this can lead to a more positive workplace environment and increased employee pride and loyalty.

Key words: Environmental, Social, Governance, employee engagement, sustainability and performance.

Introduction:

The term ESG was first coined in 2004 in the report “Who Cares Wins” issued by the United Nations Global Compact. Which stated that ‘better consideration of environmental, social and governance factors will ultimately contribute to stronger and more resilient investment markets, as well as contribute to the sustainable development of societies. As indicated, the ESG acronym stands for the following: environmental, social and governance. An environmental, social, and governance framework (ESG) is a tool with which companies can assure investors, staff, and stakeholders of their commitment to managing risk and taking opportunities related to environmental, social, and governance issues. Embracing ESG is a means by which an enterprise can not only realize its desire to be a responsible community member, but can help attract investment and talent. ESG hasn’t always gone by the same name. Centuries ago, it was seen as social or moral responsibility. This involved engaging with the local community and intending to support the disadvantaged

Today ESG consideration is increasingly seen as crucial for assessing a company’s long-term sustainability and performance. It has a profound impact on corporate reputation and brand value, as organizations recognized for strong ESG practices tend to enjoy better public perception and customer loyalty. It’s determining investment decisions, shaping business strategies, and influencing the global economy. It’s a mirror of the shared values between companies, their customers and communities. Many are embracing a holistic view of ESG, going past environmental sustainability alone.

ESG monitoring is a significant challenge for large organization, as many cannot manage or measure it independently. ESG criteria are subjective, making it challenging for investors to compare companies’ ESG practices. Implementing these criteria can be costly, especially for smaller companies, The present study conducted on Universal automobile and Dairy products, Mysore to analyze the role of Environmental Social and Governance in workplace.

Statement of the problem:

ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance), are increasingly growing factors of importance for companies to measure within their supply and value chains. A strong ESG framework now reflects greatly on an organization’s brand and how it is viewed by investors and broader stakeholder groups such as customers, suppliers and the community. As the world becomes more aware of the impact of climate change and social issues, ESG has

become a vital part of business and investment decisions. It provides a framework for organizations to manage risks and opportunities related to sustainability issues. This overview of ESG has highlighted the key components of ESG, its importance in today's world, and how it has evolved over time. ESG issues for employees include fair wages, safe conditions, rights, diversity, inclusion, training, and work-life balance, requiring a supportive workplace culture, fair compensation, occupational health, and professional growth opportunities. So, it became very essential to analyze the impact of ESG on employees.

Need of the study:

ESG not only makes a business favorable to investors, but it can also improve the overall financial performance of a business. Even small efforts toward sustainability such as going paperless, recycling or making energy-efficient upgrades can improve a business's bottom line and Return on Investment. A strong ESG proposition can help companies attract and retain quality employees, enhance employee motivation by instilling a sense of purpose, and increased overall productivity. An effective ESG plan is demonstrated by the contribution of an organization to cost reduction, risk management and overall sustainability towards environmental challenges. It also proves that the company has a strong set of socio - economic values.

Scope of the study:

The study will cover the concept of employee's engagement and motivation for ESG, it also concentrates on examining how employees are engaged and motivated by ESG. Further, it attempts to analyze the impact of ESG on employees. Study also covers the analysis of the motivation level of employees of Universal Automobile and Dairy Products Mysore towards the ESG benefits offered by the company, and study also focuses on the benefits utilized by the employees in the company.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the concept of the Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG)
2. To identify the major factors contribute to ESG
3. To analyze the benefits of ESG to employees.
4. To analyze the satisfaction of employee's towards ESG implementation in the organization.

Research methodology:

The project work has been brought out on the basis of both the primary data and Secondary data as well.

Primary data:

Primary data was collected through the interaction with the employees of Universal Automobile and Dairy Products Mysore by issuing well-structured questionnaires.

Secondary data:

Secondary data was collected with the help of articles, journals research papers and websites etc.

Sample Design:

Sampling size: We considered the whole population as a sampling size.

Sample unit: The study conducted in Universal Automobile and Dairy Products Mysore.

Tools used:

The data was analyzed through the help of Ratio analysis.

Limitations:

1. The study was restricted to Mysore.
2. The study sample size limited to 116 respondents.
3. The study analysis was based on the perception and interaction with the employees of Universal Automobile and Dairy Products, Mysore.

Result and discussion:

Table 1: showing the demographic details of the respondents.

Demographic variables		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	93	80
	Female	23	20
	Total	116	100

Age	20-30	20	17
	30-40	37	32
	40-50	54	47
	50 above	5	4
	Total	116	100
Education qualification	SSLC & below	0	0
	PUC/Diploma	42	36
	Degree	28	24
	Post-graduation	46	40
	Total	116	100
Monthly salary	Below 10000	11	10
	10001-20000	58	50
	20001-30000	27	23
	Above 30001	20	17
	Total	116	100
Nature of employment	Temporary	106	91
	Permanent	10	9
	Total	116	100
Job experience	0-5	25	22
	5-10	43	36
	10-20	25	22
	Above 20	23	20
	Total	116	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that most of the respondents i.e. 80% of the respondents are male , 47% of the respondents are aged between 40-50 years , 40% of the respondents have completed post-graduation and majority i.e. 50 % of the respondents are taken 10000-20000 as monthly salary, 91% of the respondents nature of employment is temporary. The study reveals that 36% of the respondents have 5-10 years job experience.

Table 2:- showing the classification of respondents based on involved in the concept of Environmental, Social and Governance.

Sl. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	116	100
2	No	0	0
Total		116	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that majority i.e. 100% of the respondents are involved in the concept of Environmental, Social and Governance.

Table 3:- showing the classification of respondents based on their company's current area of ESG practices.

Sl. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Environmental	97	83
2	Social	17	15
3	Governance	2	2
Total		116	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that the majority i.e. 83% of the respondents is currently focusing on the environmental area, 15% of the respondents are currently focusing on the social area, and the remaining 2% of the respondents are currently focusing on the governance area.

Table 4:- showing the classification of respondents based on company's budget allocated towards ESG initiatives.

Sl. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 10%	22	19
2	10- 25%	78	67
3	25-50%	9	8
4	More than 50%	7	6
Total		116	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that the majority, i.e.67% of the respondents are express that company allocated 10 - 25% of budget towards ESG initiatives 19% of the respondents are express that less than 10 % of company budget is allocated towards ESG initiatives, 8% of the respondents express that 25 - 50% are allocated towards ESG and remaining 6% of the respondents are express that 50% budget are allocated towards ESG.

Table 5:-showing the classification of respondents based on transparent of company's ESG reporting.

Sl. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Highly transparent	28	24
2	Somewhat transparent	85	73
3	Not transparent	3	3
Total		116	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that majority i.e. 73% of the respondents are somewhat transparent in ESG reporting, 24% of the respondents are highly transparent and the remaining 3% of the respondents are not transparent in ESG reporting.

Table 6:- showing the classification of respondents based on their opinions towards environmental, social, and governance.

Sl. No	Particulars	Yes	No	Total	
1	Does your company have an ESG score or rating?	Number of Respondents	0	116	116
		Percentage	0	100	100
2	Does your firm currently advocate or being to advocacy groups for ESG issue?	Number of Respondents	0	116	116
		Percentage	0	100	100
3	Has your company set specific ESG targets or goals for the future?	Number of Respondents	103	13	116
		Percentage	89	11	100
4	Does your company conduct regular ESG audits or assessments?	Number of Respondents	104	12	116
		Percentage	90	10	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that majority i.e. 100% of the respondents does not have an ESG score or rating and do not currently advocate for or be in advocacy groups for ESG issues. Majority i.e. 90% of the respondents conduct regular ESG audits or assessments, 89% of the respondents set specific ESG targets or goals for the future.

Table 7:- shows the classification of respondents based on the factors contributing to ESG.

[A- agree, SA- strongly agree, DA- disagree, SDA- strongly disagree]

Sl no	Particulars	A	SA	DA	SDA	Total	
1	Efficient use of resources	No of respondents					116
		Percentage					100
2	Respect for human rights within the company	No of respondents					116
		Percentage					100

3	Risk management	No of respondents	55	61	0	0	116
		Percentage	47	53	0	0	100
4	Health and safety	No of respondents	63	53	0	0	116
		Percentage	54	46	0	0	100
5	Air pollution prevention technologies	No of respondents	45	71	0	0	116
		Percentage	39	61	0	0	100
6	Biodiversity	No of respondents	35	81	0	0	116
		Percentage	30	70	0	0	100
7	Clean technology	No of respondents	32	84	0	0	116
		Percentage	28	72	0	0	100
8	Coordination with local communities	No of respondents	75	41	0	0	116
		Percentage	65	35	0	0	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that respondents are strongly agree with factors, like use of resources, respect for human rights , risk management, health and safety , air pollution prevention, biodiversity , clean technology and coordination are contribute to ESG.

Table 8:- showing the classification of respondents based challenges are faced by company in implementing ESG practices. (Multiple option)

Sl. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Lack of resources	34	27
2	Awareness	59	46
3	Regulatory hurdles	6	5
4	Integration with existing processes	28	22
Total		127	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that 46% of the respondents consider awareness to be the most challenging factor in implementing ESG practices, 27% of the respondents consider lack of resources to be the most challenging factor in implementing ESG practices, 22% of the respondents consider integration with existing processes to be the most challenging factor in implementing ESG practices and the remaining 5% of the respondents consider regulatory hurdles to be the most challenging factor in implementing ESG practices.

Table 9:- showing the classification of respondents based on ESG benefits related to employees.

[SA- Strongly agree, A- Agree, N- Neutral, DA- Disagree, SDA- Strongly disagree]

Sl. No	Particulars		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total
1	Social security	No, of Respondents	18	98	0	0	0	116
		Percentage	16	84	0	0	0	100
2	Achievement	No, of	19	93	3	1	0	116

	awards	Respondents						
		Percentage	16	80	3	1	0	100
3	Health Insurance	No, of Respondents	56	58	1	1	0	116
		Percentage	48	50	1	1	0	100
4	Paid vacation	No, of Respondents	44	68	4	0	0	116
		Percentage	38	59	3	0	0	100
5	Competitive compensation (Performance-based incentives, fair wages)	No, of Respondents	38	78	0	0	0	116
		Percentage	33	67	0	0	0	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that majority i.e. 84% of the respondents are agree that social security benefits are related to employees ,80% of the respondents are agree that achievement awards benefits are related to employees, 50% of the respondents are agree that health insurance benefits are related to employees, Majority i.e.59% of the respondents are agree that paid vacation benefits are related to employees, 67% of the respondents are agree that competitive compensation benefits are related to employees.

Table 10:- showing the classification of respondents based on satisfaction of employees towards ESG implement in their organization.

[HS- Highly satisfied, S- Satisfied, N- Neutral, DS- Dissatisfied, HDS- Highly dissatisfied]

Sl. No	Particulars		HS	S	N	DS	HDS	Total
1	You are satisfied with the company's efforts to promote environmental sustainability.	No, of Respondents	24	89	3	0	0	116
		Percentage	21	76	3	0	0	100
2	You are satisfied with the company's policies on equality and non - discrimination.	No, of Respondents	17	98	1	0	0	116
		Percentage	15	84	1	0	0	100
3	How satisfied are you with the resources	No. of Respondents	35	79	2	0	0	116
		Percentage	30	68	2	0	0	100

	& support provided to engage with ESG initiatives?							
4	How satisfied are you with your company's overall commitment to ESG principles?	No, of Respondents	23	91	2	0	0	116
		Percentage	20	78	2	0	0	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that majority i.e. 76% of the respondents are satisfied with the company's efforts to promote environmental sustainability. 84% of the respondents are satisfied with the company's policies on equality and non -discrimination, Majority i.e. 68% of the respondents are satisfied with the resources & support provided to engage with ESG initiatives. Majority i.e.78% of the respondents are satisfied with company's overall commitment to ESG principles.

Findings:

- ❖ 83% of the respondents are agreeing that the efficient use of resources contributes towards ESG, majority i.e. 61% of the respondents are agree that air pollution prevention technologies contribute towards ESG, majority i.e. 70% of the respondents are agree that biodiversity factors contribute towards ESG, majority i.e. 72% of the respondents are agree that clean technologies contribute towards ESG, and majority i.e. 65% of the respondents are strongly agree that coordination with the local community contributes towards ESG.
- ❖ Majority i.e. 53% of the respondents are considered they have a risk management committee or officer and risk management contribute towards ESG.
- ❖ Majority i.e. 84% of the respondents are agree that social security (ESG) benefits are related to employees.
- ❖ The above table shows that majority i.e. 76% of the respondents are satisfied with the company's efforts to promote environmental sustainability. 84% of the respondents are satisfied with the company's policies on equality and non –discrimination.

Suggestions:

- ❖ **Green Office Initiatives:** - Implement green office practices such as reducing paper usage, recycling programs, or energy-saving measures. Involve employees in these initiatives and recognize their contributions.
- ❖ **Training and Skill Development:** - Offer training sessions or workshops on topics related to sustainability, such as energy efficiency, waste reduction, or ethical sourcing. Employees can gain valuable skills and knowledge while contributing to ESG goals.
- ❖ **Communication and Transparency:** - Examine the role of transparent communication in fostering employee trust and engagement in ESG initiatives. Highlight effective communication strategies that organizations can employ to keep employees informed and involved.

Conclusion:

Embracing ESG principles is not only beneficial for the environment and society but also essential for ensuring governance and achieving sustainable financial performance. The present study was found that employees are properly utilizing the available benefits of ESG and this can lead to a more positive workplace environment and increased employee pride and loyalty. ESG initiatives can drive innovation by encouraging sustainable practices and social responsibility. This can lead to the development of new products, services, and processes that enhance productivity and efficiency.

Finally, to conclude if the Strong ESG performance enhances a company's reputation, making it more appealing to stakeholders, including employees. Incorporating ESG factors helps companies manage risks more effectively, including those related to environmental regulations, social unrest, and governance scandals.

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